

THE LEVEL OF RESILIENT AMONG GIFTED AND TALENTED STUDENTS IN MALAYSIA

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Abstract

This paper discusses the level of resilient among gifted and talented students in Malaysia. The level of high resilient will be impact on the social and academic. The concept of this paper aims to identify the extent level of resilient among gifted and talented students to achieve excellent academic results. Many gifted and talented students plagued with various problems concerning environment and everyday life such as social and environmental problems, peer and social culture, followed by issues of social activity lessons, future career, and entertainment, in addition, alot of problems such as food service and social relations with peers in hostels. Resilient is individual skill to be able to adapt in the face of the social environment and the learning environment so that it can be calm and give motivation in academic achievement. Previous studies found resilient can be to the impact on the lives among gifted and talented students. When individuals have the levels of high resilient will be able to face and solve the problems encountered in everyday life. This showed that the resilient can be increased to achieve individual skills in dealing with problems in themselves and others. Therefore, the authors recommend that the actual research to identify issues for understanding resilience among gifted and talented students.

Keyword: Resilient, Gifted, Talented, Students

Introduction

Student is a status that is carries by students who studies at School. At the learning session there is a change in the life and spirit of the individual. Individuals always want to be brilliant, scintillating and fairly. It is thus a dynamic dream that glory is still largely dependent on the individual strengths in terms of mental, physical and intellectual. Many students under pressure and change when entering a new realm boarding school far from home. Pressure experienced by students have continuity with the adjustment to the environments and become a severe problem by students to adapt. In general, many students want to gain experience, learn the system and a new culture. (King and Ruiz-Gelices 2003; Mohamad Kamal Harun, 2009; Ka Ho Mok, 2011).

According to Connor (2006), the ability to solve the problems or stresses in life changes faced by people is always unstable. Similarly, the term resilient behavior experts in resilience and durability problems always occur in students who in the dorm. Life in boarding schools will face challenges and difficulties. The difficulties will affect their lives. Half of the people cannot faced the situation and challenges of life, making them stress and not be satisfy (Siebert 2005; Masten & Coatsworth, 1998; Pearson & Hall, 2006). Gifted talented students have higher achievement in the academic field. However, when academic achievement is low it will make gifted students become stressed and did not receive the test results. This makes the endurance or resilient of students is low and not good.

Feldman (2011) states that people has high resilient can controlled the emotion in faced a challanges. people who can adapt their-self and adapt with surroundings it will produce good resilient and positif emotion that can solve the problems surroundings (Yahaya 2005; Shazli, Ponnusamy, Normah & Nik Farideh (2006). Resilient uses as the general capability which involves high adaptability and flexibility when faced with inside and outside problems. Andrew (1974) said that an individu who has resilient can adapt with new situation.

Block Klohnen (1996), states that resilient has a relation with the gifted and talented students. Gifted and talented students has high motivation and high desire. It is linked to the individual emotion in face a challenges in academic life. Resilient be able gives motivation to yourself and if faced some challenges. According to Aluwis (2012) explain that many students has problem be affected by new surroundings, social relations, culture and far away from family that effect cannot accept the fact. (Emmy E. Werner & Smith 1992; Emmy E. Werner, 2003; Desmita, 2005).

Many factors effect the resilient to gifted and talented students such as socio-cultural, new surrounding, unstable emotion and food factor (Abd Hair Awang, Zaimah Ramli dan Izzurazila ibrahim, 2012). Communication (Hayani, 2004) and Resilient (Smith, 2008). Refers to these factors, Resilient is an important element which should be given attention.

Smith (2008) discuss about resilient positive student will gives positive impression to academic achievment. It will gives impact like responsibility, self-confident good communication with social. Safe individuals will have good resilient as talkative, less socializing, having a joint character, self-confident, do not panic and think independently (Hogan, Johnson, and Briggs, 1997; Pervin, L. & John, 1999; Samuel D.

Gosling, Peter J. Rentfrow, and William B. Swann Jr., 2003)

The conclusions, gifted and talented students need good resilient in faced problems in their life. Resilient factor will makes people excited and satisfied because feeling spacious and avoid pressures in daily lifes. People who has good resilient will adapt easily with the new surroundings. Therefore, resilient has important role the gifted talented students have character and attitude of perfectionism.

Definition of gifted and talented students

The concept of cleverness comes from the term of intelligence derived from the word *intelgentia* (creation of the Greek philosophers, Cicerio). According to Plato was the first person that distinguish the influence of genes and environment on intelligence before Galton. According to Wechsler is the ability to understand the environment, ourselves and expertise that can help individuals to solve life's challenges. According to Alfred Binet is the ability to adapt and self-critical reasoning. Francis Galton, Cartell & Hall of intelligence is inherited. The human development basicly determined and cannot be changed and wise person who comes from a lineage of sages only.

The term of gifted and intelligent has been used by Francis Galton in 1869. The term of gifted and intelligent introduced by Guy M. Whipple in 1920. The concept of gifted is a formal term for reffering the children who have outstanding ability of intellectual.

According to Davis & Rimm (1985) divides the intelligent into 5 categories:

1. Based on the level of achievement in any field of endeavor
2. Based on achievement scores in a test of intelligence
3. Based on a percent (%) achievement test
4. Based on natural talent in a particular field or several fields
5. Based on creativity

The deinition of gifted children and talented legal to education act gifted talented and intelligent (Gifted & Talented Educational Act 1978), according to public law 100-297, The Federal Definition of Gifted and Talented in NCLB (No Child Left Behind Act of 2001 US) "Gifted Intetelligent and Talented" (gifted and talented) refers to s intelligent and talented children and teenagers shows proof of high achievement capability in intellectual, creativity, artistic, or leadership capacity, or in specific academic, and those who need of not normal services or activities provided by the school to expand its capabilities that is listed above (Joseph Renzulli's Three-Ring Conception of Giftedness 1978).

The Characteristic of Gifted and Talented Students

There are three main features of gifted people first, high intellectual, second, high creativity and motivation third high commitment in completing the assignment. According Rysiew, Shore & Carson 1994 expound that the gifted and talented students very important to note especially in the resilient because many people cannot accepting the reality when his academic achievement is low. The characteristic of gifted and talented students are:

1. Students have many choices.
2. Multi potential students also become the perfection, so they look to be perfect or ideal desired results.
3. Students liked taciturn

4. Gifted and talented students are less of socializing
5. Students are not communicating.

Characteristic of talented children have excelled in one or more areas of work such as drama, art, music, leadership and differences between gifted and talented developed by Howard Gardner in eight areas of intelligent (verbal-linguistic, kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, logic-mathmatic, music, visual-spatial / spatial, naturalist). Characteristics of the talented students is unique personality, emotional and sensitif, less of friendly or the other way, influential, Specific skill, have one hobby only, High motivation, interpersonal skills, Standout, Not arrogant, Artistic, intrapersonal skills or love to treat own feelings (Silverman 2012).

Characteristics of the gifted children is has an intellectual above the average which high academic achievement and high creativity. Characteristics of the gifted children are: see in the early age, love to ask a question, able to work alone, various interest, love to investigates, fun learning, many information, long-term focus, powerful, intrinsically motivated, sense of humor, honest, critical and judgmental, idealistic, open mind about the cause-effect of the relationship.

Definition of Resilient

Resilient introduced by (Redl 1969) used to adapt from individual conditions. (Smith 2008). According to (Grotberg 1999) define resilient is the ability of individuals to adapt with the problem faced. Luthar & Cicchetti (2000) states that resilient means individual skills in order to solve the negative problem. Such as positive thinking in face of not achieve desire can solve problem from negative effects. According to (Reivich & Shatte, 2002) resilient is an ability to adapt and keep the spirit in difficult conditions such as the students that are difficult to adapt in new environment, life is difficult in set the time, the pressure that always comes up continually, the unpredictable events in the environment. (Emmy E. Werner & Smith 1992; Emmy E. Werner, 2003; Desmita, 2005).

Skills that must have to individuals who have high resilient or recovering from stress condition, trauma and full of risks, people need some skill in resilient (Emmy E. Werner & Smith, 1992:227) are:

1. Efficiency to create relationships (social competence),
2. Problem-solving skills (metacognition),
3. Skills to develop a sense of identity (autonomy),
4. Planning and hope (an understanding of the objectives and future).

Resilient Factors

(Reivich & Shatte 2002; Suwarjo 2008) states that there are seven factors of capability can be used to create resilient individual level, are:

1. Emotion regulation

Individual's ability to stay calm faced the pressure is called emotion regulation. People who have difficulties controlling the emotion often satisfying emotion to others, because others are difficult to work well together. People who has resilient have been able to use the set of developed skill to help control the emotions, attention and behavior.

2. Impulse control

(Reivich & Shatte 2002) believes that this relationship in belief system of individual. The ability to control the impulse or low impulse control, people will receive the first impulse in his belief about a situation as something right and will act on impulse. Consequently, people often act rashly, less working-out mature. People with poor impulse control often excited desire as a job, and without thinking trying to catch the job though not accordance with ability. Impulse control is the individuals ability to organize and control that appear in him-self. Included in this capability is the ability to suspend a desire. Impulse control is very relates with emotional control. Individuals who have a good ability to control impulse is likely have a good ability to control emotions.

3. Optimist

Optimist is a belief that can change for the better, and future outlook as a relatively bright future. Resilient people believe on tomorrow and sure he can afford better way of life. Optimist implicate that people believes he has the ability to overcome “adversity” that cannot be avoided in the future. Therefore, people who are optimistic looks the future of them relatively brighter. Healthy Optimist is positive and optimistic reality because not reality optimists can bring people into action of underestimate the real threats that need to be anticipates and overcomes.

4. Causal analysis

Causal analysis is individual’s ability to solve quickly and precisely the problem faced. If someone is not able to measuring the problem quickly and precisely then he will making the same mistakes over and over again. This capability includes the ability to consider and explore the good and bad things that happen to people. This ability is related to the style of thinking "explanatory style thinking" of individual.

5. Empathy

Empathy is the ability of individuals to read signs (cue, gesture, expression) which describes the psychological and emotional conditions that is experiencing by others. Most of skilled individuals interpret non-verbal expression (facial expressions, tone of voice, body language), and the thoughts and feelings of others. Meanwhile, the other people do not develop those skills that are not able to put themselves in the "others", cannot estimate what the other person have to feel, and cannot predict what other people love to do. It thus would be very damage to the individual's relationship with others. People with low emphaty tend to repeat patterns of behavior that are not resilient, and tend to generalize the feelings and desires of others

6. Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is the sense of the individual that gives effective in the world. The sense illustrates an individual's belief that he is able to solve problems that may be experienced, and sure that he was having the ability to succeed. Self-efficacy is the belief and someone assessment of his ability to organize and implement measures to achieve a certain level of performance expected. People with high self-efficacy tend to focus their attention and efforts on the demands of the task and try to minimize the difficulties to the case.

7. Reaching out

Open yourself is the ability for the people to having a relationships with others, looking for new experiences, seeking the wealth meaning of life, looking for deep relationships, and commit to the learning effort and search for new experiences. There are three important aspects in reaching out, there are, a) can be a good

measure of risk that can distinguish the risks are reasonable and unreasonable, b) understanding yourself well so it feels comfortable in expressing thoughts and feelings, c) find the meaning and purpose of life as well as appreciative of what he had experienced. Open yourself have a risk. Make friends with new people, try something new, looking for activities that provide meaning in life requires a large amount of self-encouragement and strength. The risk of failure, rejection of others, shame, disappointed, sadness, a portion that needs to be measure in opening up (reaching out).

Therefore, Thus, many factors faced by people in resilient. People who have a good resilient will be able to adapt to the difficulties problem, in order to be calm and to rise from adversity faced and rediscover the passion, power, and purpose of reality.

The Characteristics of Individuals Who Have Resilient

The characteristics of individuals who have positive resilient according to Sarfino (1994), are:

- a. Have a calmer temperament, that it can create better relationships with family and environments.
- b. Has the ability to be able to rise from the pressure and trying to overcome the problems faced.

On the other hand, Gortberg (1995), also said that people who has resilient there are some of the characteristics:

- a. Has the ability to control feelings and impulse in the heart.
- b. Has the ability to be able to rise up and give motivation of the problem and trying to solve the problems faced in surroundings.
- c. Has attitude and independent and can make decisions based on their own ideas and initiatives and have empathy and high caring towards the problem of other people.

Reivich (2002), states that people who has resilient has certain characteristic there are (a) able to overcome the stress; (b) be realistic and optimistic in resolving the problem; (c) be able to express their thoughts and feelings comfortably.

Then it can be concluded that the characteristics of individuals who have a resilient can control the feelings and able to express comfortably and has independent attitude and empathy with the environments. Therefore, the individual is able to take a positive decision, Then it can be concluded that the characteristics of individuals who have a resilient can control the feelings and able to express comfortably and has independent attitude and empathy with the environments. Therefore, the individual is able to take a positive decision, reality and optimistic to resolve the problems faced and people who have a caring attitude towards fellow students.

Discussion

According to (Bonano, Rennie and Dekel, 2007; Rinaldi, 2010) states that resilient gives effect to the students such as emotional factor, environment, gender, age, nation, educational or teaching program, the level of trauma, income, social support, the frequency of chronic diseases, the stresses of life past and present.

Hiew (2000), states that resilient level of resilient among the students has low resilient because less adapt to the new environments and always sick with the new environments. Janas (2002), also states that resilient needs capacity to solve difficulties, the frustration, stress, depression, and all the problems from the people itself. Sarafino (1994), also suggest that people who has resilient can rise from the peressure, stress, depression, also try to resolve it. the opinion of the experts, The opinion of experts, in accordance with the result of great research that good people adapt to the new environment, it will have high resilient (Frank 2007).

However, previous studies, Mhd Subhan (2014) states that a high level of resilience that has the relationship between talented and gifted students with gender. Based on the gender found that there was no significant differences. no differences between male and female students resilient score. However, according to (Mancini and Bonano 2006; Rinaldi, 2010) found that there were significant differences between men and women. This study shows that men have more resilient than the women. In the same investigation was conducted by Rinaldi (2010) who studied on Resilient Communities in Padang seen from Gender. The result of the investigation found that there were differences resilient followed by sex between men and women. As this study also shows that higher resilient based on gender is men resilient againts women resilient.

Therefore, the relationships of resilient with the smart and gifted students have relevance in overcoming the problems. Cause students who have resilient will be able to solve their problems and stable emotions in the face of problems in daily life.

Conclusion

Over all it can be conclude that this paper suggests that this study was able to create a concept of paper outlining the concept of resilient in the gifted and talented student. Published on previous studies that there is a difference between men and women resilient have significant difference in academic achievement (Mhd Subhan 2014). In addition, the resilient it has related to gifted and talented students. However, when the gifted and talented students have a positive resilient then the student emotional and endurance will be stable in the face of challenges. Therefore, it is expects that this paper will contribute to listeners in identifying the level of resilient among gifted and talented student. in order to have a change periodically (Janet and Lesley 2014).

Implication

This paper can be escort to the counselor and the administration school because resilient of gifted and talented students in Malaysia need adapt with the new envirotnments. It can makes the students faced the challenges in the school an in the dorm. Meanwhile, the counselor allowed to help students who have problem in resilient or endurance with the new environments. If the students is left to the problems will effect to academic, social and so on. In addition the officers can create a program to improve student resilient as executing camp that will enhance students' high level of confidence and provides confidence to his own self to solve the problem itself.

Supported by Gustissa (2012) research findings that the counseling had a significant influence on the resilient students performed before and after counseling to students. It shows that the counselor has an important role to help students who have problems that

would lead to lower student resilient. In additions of that, the counselor also can improve students' motivation and confidence in daily life. This suggestion is in line with result of Bloom et al (in Mardiah, 2003) that people who have the high confidence, capability to make decisions, because it has given training that the material is self-efficacy and optimistic that makes people sure and increase motivation and it is able to adapt with the environment so that it can help develop students resilient.

Recommendation

Research needs to run to make real interpretation. Cause real research more important to recognize the level of resilient among gifted and talented students. In a study that surveyed a raise sample it be nice and pretty in the actual study. In addition, for the next researcher to investigate the other factors other factors that influence the resilience that has not been disclosed in this research in order to obtain more complete description resilient as personality, a strong person (hardiness), competence, self-efficacy and more as one of the variables to the next researcher. So the result can be used as data to develop individual skills and used by various stakeholders to help the individual to anticipate and solve various problems that they faced.

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